

Recruitment Process, Organizational Performance: Does Employees Commitment Mediate in the Manufacturing Sector of Pakistan?

Fadillah Ismail, Fazal ur Rehman, Azhar Ud Din, Muhammad Mujtaba Asad, Farwida Javed, Sadia Ijaz Shiekh

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 04, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Recruitment process, Organizational performance, Employee's commitment, Social exchange theory</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5645433</p>	<p><i>This study intends to evaluate the effects of recruitment process on organizational performance along with mediating role of employee's commitment in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan based on the social exchange theory. The study has collected data from 384 managerial staff of the manufacturing organizations in Hattar, Islamabad, and Lahore regions. The collected data was analyzed using multiple regressions to find results. The results of the study indicated that recruitment process has positive significant effects on the organizational performance and employee's commitment in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan. The results have also indicated that employee's commitment mediated the relationship between recruitment process and organizational performance in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan. However, this study is only limited to the manufacturing sector of Pakistan in the context of social exchange theory. This study has clarified the effects of recruitment process on the organizational performance along with the mediating role of employee's commitment in the defined context. Concisely, by integrating recruitment process, organizational performance, and employee's commitment literature, the main contribution of this article is the analysis of job specification, job description, job evaluation in enhancing the organizational performance in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

The increasing competition in the market has shifted organizational focus from production efficiency to organizational and operational efficiency in many organizations around the world. This trend has been augmented the importance of human resource management in achieving the competitive advantages in marketplace and emerged as one of the strategic tools for sustainable organizational performance. However, to improve efficiency in performance, organizations are striving to recruit key valuable human capital. Organizations are devising various strategies to carefully recruit the most suitable employees to maintain the working performance and enhance the level of innovation. Employees are vital for the operation of every organization as they create value within organizations and develop organizational life and ethical climate (Gould-Williams, 2003), and contribute considerable benefits to the organizations. Today, the recruitment process has attained primary attention, because every organization wants to select those employees which can play their leading and efficient role for the achievement of organizational mission. As the efficiency in recruitment process has significant role in the organizational performance (Chen, Qiao & Lee, 2014), that can be of different types (Locke, 1970), such as job performance, financial performance and operational performance. Each type of organizational performance is necessary for the organization to sustain in highly competitive environment (Kozlowski *et al.*, 2001), and recruitment process is important for each type of organizational performance.

In addition, the significance of employee commitment is quite evident in previous literature regarding the relationship between commitment of employees and performance of organizations (Presslee, Vance & Webb, 2013). Most often, it is necessary for every organization to hire the employees who can work beyond their regular job description and perform extra roles as per the organizational requirements. However, it is also the part of every organization to hire employees who possess the capabilities of multiple task and extra activities (Anitha, 2014). Therefore, in today working environment, job performance is considered as a tool to quantify employee's job performance. This study assess the role of recruitment process in enhancing the efficiency of organizational performance along with the mediating role of employees commitment in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan based on social exchange theory. However, this study contributes to the relevant literature by analyzing the impacts of recruitment process, employees commitment on the organizational performance based on social exchange theory in Pakistani context in the manufacturing sector. This study merges the literature of recruitment process, employees commitment and the organizational performance based on the findings from

emerging economy. However, this study starts with introduction followed by literature review to explain the conceptions of defined constructs along with the theoretical framework. Methodology is in third while results are plainly explained in the fourth section of this study. Discussion, implications and conclusion are presented in the last part of this study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Social Exchange Theory

The concept of social exchange theory was introduced by Homans in 1958 with the aim to realize the social behavior of human and is the extension of economic exchange between two parties. According to the theory, the mutual exchange exists when assistance is provided by both involved parties. Even though no promises are made but still there exists the hope of future collaboration (Kelliher & Anderson, 2010). The social exchange theory describes the dependency of individual in general where one part gets monetary benefits while other party gains the personal benefits (Molm, 2006). Therefore, the social exchange association is dynamic, shared and continuing (Blau, 1964). This type of relationship among the parties is not short term like one-time transaction but in fact it is the long term relationship (Molm, 2006). Therefore, the efficiency in recruitment process can reward better performance to organization as well as employees commitment.

2.2 Organizational Performance

In the era of globalization, organizations are facing aggressive competition and feeling difficulties to achieve a competitive advantage over the competitors through customer satisfaction, operations, and financing as well as sustainability in their performance. Hence, to survive in this intense competitive environment, organizational performance has become the important area and prime focus for many organizations. Resultantly, most of the time, organizational performance is considered as an outcome of the activities of firm over a longer period of time (Osundina & sounding, 2012). Concisely, the process to enhance the well-being and effectiveness of the organization through planned intervention is known as organizational performance. Therefore, the development of organization has an impact on the learning of the organization which leads to improve the performance of the organization. It is one of the key points by which organizations are developed (Morales, 2012). Exactly, several definitions are presented for organizational performance in prior studies. Such as, Khandekar and Sharma (2006) have defined organizational performance as the result to show and reflect the inefficiencies and efficiencies of organizations in terms of financial performance, competencies and brand image (Khandekar & Sharma, 2006). Widely, job performance, financial performance and operations performance are perceived as the bigger elements of organizational performance.

2.3 Recruitment and Selection Process

Prior literature has highlighted the four important dimensions of the selection and recruitment process such as (1) job description, (2) job specification, (3) job evaluation, and (4) job analysis. In the organizational research, the recruitment process has enormous importance and a fundamental role in human resource management. How to attract the suitable and appropriate candidates towards the organization is often a challenge and comprehensive program for many organizations. By this recruitment program, the organizations choose, attract, acquire and appoint the candidates who possess a set of skills. Concisely, the process of recruitment and selection in an organization plays an essential part to mold and shape the firm performance, validation and its efficiency, and firms possess the capacity to attract and hire the employees with fresh knowledge, relevant skills, and proficiency along with the abilities to accurately predict future. Furthermore, it is often claimed that selecting workers is not only hiring the employees but to bring well qualified and skillful workforce who can deliver in efficient manner (Ballantyne, 2009). However, hiring, promotion, job posting, transfer are the important functions of the recruitment process.

2.4 Employee's Commitment

Since 1950s, workplace commitment is the topic of interest for academia as well as practitioners (Cohen, 2003). It has attracted concentration due to manager's and organizational analyst's curiosity to explore ideas and enhance employee performance (Steers, 1977). However, it is a fact that employee commitment positively influences the organizational performance (Nijhof *et al.*, 1998), as well as the employees themselves (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). However, many aspects of this positive influence are yet needed to be explored with many possible responses. Meyer and Herscovitch (2001) have asserted that various kinds of commitments in the workplace can enhance the employee performance. However, the organizational commitment definition explains the feeling of commitment as an involvement (Mowday *et al.*, 1979), attachment (Meyer & Allen, 1996) or commitment (Brown, 1996) to the organization. Porter and Smith (1970, as cited in Mowday *et al.*, 1979) have caters the organizational commitment in the context of involvement such as; "the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization". While Brown (1996) has proposed organizational commitment as the devotion and provision for the organization that increases the expectations and reward related to the job.

2.5 Relationship between recruitment process and organization performance

In the present era of globalization, the market trend has shifted towards sophisticated economy while recruitment has developed to be a vital instrument for the firms to ensure human capital asset which is needed to gain their present strategic path and to continue innovation and future growth. The functions of recruitment are the outcomes of strategic planning of human resources management functions, whereas simultaneously, recruitment is the input contribution of employee selection and their placement procedure. The certain strategy of human resource management regulates the sources of recruitment and makes set-up of appropriate programs for the recruitment to bring desired human talent in the workplace (Bogatova, 2017). The process of recruitment in generally has described to be a set of actions and procedures utilized to attain the desired number of competent employees at their suitable place at a suitable time. This is done so that the individuals and firms might choose one another with their best suited short as well as long term interests (Biong, Nygaard, & Silkoset, 2010). Simply, the process of recruitment provides a pool of competent and appropriate candidates to select workers to get achieve the organizational goals.

H1: There is a positive significant relationship between the recruitment process and organizational performance.

2.6 Relationship between recruitment process and employee's commitment

The values of organization play a critical role in the effective selection and recruitment process as organizational culture plays a critical role in hiring the right person for right job. Moreover, the detail of job is to inform a person in the process of evaluation during the recruitment process (Armstrong, 2000a). To keep employee informed regarding equal employment opportunities is concerned with the job description through which each and every requirement and prerequisite of the jobs are communicated to the applicants (McGrath & Hammontree, 2016). In order to screen the employees, potential employees are assessed on individual and group basis through exercises, questionnaires, and tests. These assessment methods are used to analyze and screen the applicants and to assess their character as well. Moreover, employees are assessed in terms of their suitability for the job and the key information regarding job are communicated to the employees as well (Armstrong, 2000a). A proper process of recruitment and selection is to communicate the importance of hiring the right employees for organization which develop the commitment among candidates who get selected for the job (Armstrong, 2000a).

H2: There is a positive significant relationship between the recruitment process and employee's commitment.

2.7 Relationship between employee's commitment and organizational performance

Traditionally, organizations provide value to improve employee commitment as it is the cause of reduction in withdrawal attitude of employees like turnover, lateness, and absenteeism of employees. Therefore, this behavior shows serious results in the performance of organizations. Lo (2009) has noted that committed employees get engaged in withdrawal behavior and can easily admit required change. Thus, this withdrawal behavior gives consequences for the employees as they are the foundation of organizational life. While, less committed employees can direct their commitment attitude to other paths, can significantly find other paths to improve organization, and also get retained. Thus, it is important to know how to develop the right type and level of employee's commitment to ensure that the better employees are retained. Committed employees are highly satisfied and they fulfill their job very well. In the present global economic setting, change in the organizational settings is continues procedure that need the help of the workers in the organizational hierarchy.

H3: There is a positive significant relationship between employee's commitment and organizational performance.

2.8 The mediating role of employee's commitment between recruitment process and organizational performance

Previous literature noted that recruitment process has positive and statistically significant association with the organizational performance but this study is interested to examine the mediating role of employee's commitment between dependent and independent variable. Previous studies have less focused to empirically examine the mediating effects of employee's commitment between the two variables specifically in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan. However, this study is focusing on to fill up the identified gap of knowledge and assesses the mediating role of employee's commitment between recruitment process and organizational performance in the emerging economy. Therefore, this study has hypothesized as;

H4: There is mediating role of employee's commitment on the relationship between recruitment process and organizational performance

2.9 Research Framework

On the basis of previous literature and the gap of knowledge, this study has proposed the following model to hypothesize the relationship among variables. This study has proposed recruitment process as independent variable, employee's commitment as mediating variable, and organizational performance as dependent variable in the Pakistani context.

3. Methodology

This study has collected data through questionnaires based survey from 384 managerial staff members (Based on Krejcie and Morgan Table) of manufacturing sector in Hattar, Islamabad, and Lahore regions of Pakistan. The motivation in the adoption of quantitative approach in current research is to help the scholars to show signs of improved understanding that utilize statistical instruments and to understand connections among variables of the research (Given & Lisa, 2008). Quantitative research is particularly used for empirical data and observation, which implies that quantitative approach, is the important part to deal about assessing the effects and causes of specific phenomena and then uses the gathered data by observation techniques (Briffa, 2001). This study has utilized already reliable and valid Self-Administered Questionnaire. The measurement of each variable is described in the following table. The study has used Likert scale to measure each item in the questionnaire which is a bipolar scale technique and measures the negative/positive response to the statements asked from the respondents (Carifio *et al.*, 2007). The Likert scale involves statement which is responded by respondents based on subjective or objective criteria. Generally, the measurement is done based on agreement or disagreement level of respondents regarding the statement. They are typically used five levels for answering the responses given following (Likert, 1932): Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, and Strongly Agree.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variable	Measurement Factors	No of items
Recruitment and Selection Process	Job Description	5
	Job Specification	5
	Job Evaluation	5
	Job Analysis	5
Employee's Commitment	Affective Commitment	6
	Normative Commitment	6
	Continuance Commitment	6
Organizational Performance	Financial Performance	6
	Job Performance	6
	Operational Performance	6
Total number of items		56

4. Results

Table.2 shows the reliability of the applied scale to ensure the accuracy of study conduction. The reliability coefficient Cronbach's Alpha of each variable separately (Recruitment process, Employee commitment, and Organizational performance) is presented in the below table.

Table 2: Reliability of each variable

Variable name	Reliability Coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha)	Number of Items	Reliability level
Recruitment process	0.874	20	Very Good
Employee commitment	0.863	18	Very Good
Organizational performance	0.885	18	Very Good

4.1 Regression Analysis

The regression analysis can be applied to evaluate the relationship between selected variables of the study as well as testing the developed hypothesis. The study has applied multiple linear regressions analysis to examine the relation of all independent variables with dependent variable. However, in hypothesis testing, the goal is to examine the value of probability (p) whether the test results are equal or less than their appropriate significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$). It predicts the size of problematic region or size of test. *The values of R and R²* in table 3 indicate how well the model predicts the observation on the variance and variability between recruitment process (job description, job evaluation, job specification, and job analysis) and organizational performance. In the results of model summary, in the first step of the correlation coefficient $R = 0.320$ indicates a considerable degree of correlation between job description and the organizational performance. The value of R-Square shows

the degree of variation in the organizational performance which has explained by job description. Reading the value of $R^2 = 0.103$ suggests that (10.3%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained and interpreted by job description. In the step 2, the correlation coefficient $R = .378$ has further increased with the addition of job evaluation. The value of R-Square = 0.143 suggests that (14.3%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained by job description and job evaluation. In step 3, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.541$ has increased due to the addition of job specification. The value of R-Square = 0.292 suggests that (29.2%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained by job description, job evaluation, job specification. In the last step, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.541$ has remained the same even with the addition of job analysis and no further changes were noted in the value of R-Square.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.320 ^a	.103	.100		.5360
2	.378 ^b	.143	.138		.5247
3	.541 ^c	.292	.286		.4774
4	.541 ^d	.293	.285		.47797

The results of multiple regressions in model have shown that job description has positive significant ($B = 0.274$) effects on the organizational performance in manufacturing sector of Pakistan. In the second step, the addition of job evaluation has decreased the value of job description from ($B = 0.274$) to ($B = 0.160$), while job evaluation has positive significant ($B = 0.203$) effects on the organizational performance. In step three, job specification has positive significant ($B = 0.340$) effects on the organizational performance, while the effects of job description and job evaluation have dropped down. In the final step, job analysis has positive insignificant ($B = 0.018$) effects on the organizational performance, while the values of other variables have slightly dropped down. In conclusion, recruitment process has positive significant ($B = .624$) effects on the organizational performance in manufacturing sector of Pakistan.

Table 4: Results of Multiple Regressions

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Job.Des	.274	.042	.320	6.454	.000	1.000
2	Job.Des	.160	.050	.188	3.215	.001	1.442
	Job.eva	.203	.049	.240	4.108	.000	1.442
3	Job.Des	.120	.046	.141	2.633	.009	1.457
	Job.eva	.139	.045	.164	3.050	.002	1.481
	Job.Spec	.340	.039	.402	8.750	.000	1.079
4	Job.Des	.119	.046	.139	2.602	.010	1.462
	Job.eva	.137	.046	.162	2.981	.003	1.499
	Job.Spec	.335	.040	.397	8.304	.000	1.164
	Job.Ana	.018	.044	.020	.415	.678	1.148
5	Rec. Pro	.624	.057	.495	10.859	.000	1.94

Secondly, in the results of model summary, in the first step of the correlation coefficient $R = .267$ indicates a considerable degree of correlation between job description and the employees commitment. The value of R-Square shows the degree of variation in the employees commitment which has explained by job description. Reading the value of $R^2 = 0.071$ suggests that (7.1%) of the variance in employees commitment can be explained and interpreted by job description. In the step 2, the correlation coefficient $R = .325$ has further increased with the addition of job evaluation. The value of R-Square = 0.105 suggests that (10.5%) of the variance in employees commitment can be explained by job description and job evaluation. In step 3, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.373$ has increased due to the addition of job specification. The value of R-Square = 0.139 suggests that (13.9%) of the variance in employees commitment can be explained by job description, job evaluation, job specification. In the last step, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.376$ has slightly increases with the addition of job analysis. The value of R-Square = 0.141 suggests that (14.1%) of the variance in employees commitment.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.267 ^a	.071	.069	.54235
2	.325 ^b	.105	.101	.53301
3	.373 ^c	.139	.132	.52363

4	.376 ^d	.141	.132	.52370
---	-------------------	------	------	--------

The results of multiple regressions in model have shown that job description has positive significant ($B = 0.227$) effects on the employees commitment in manufacturing sector of Pakistan. In the second step, the addition of job evaluation has decreased the value of job description from ($B = 0.227$) to ($B = 0.123$), while job evaluation has positive significant ($B = 0.187$) effects on the employees commitment. In step three, job specification has positive significant ($B = 0.160$) effects on the employees commitment, while the effects of job description and job evaluation have dropped down. In the final step, job analysis has positive and insignificant ($B = 0.046$) effects on the employees commitment, while the values of other variables have slightly dropped down. In conclusion, recruitment process has positive significant ($B = .461$) effects on the employees commitment in manufacturing organization.

Table 6: Results of Multiple Regressions

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Job.Des	.227	.043	.267	5.287	.000	1.000
2	Job.Des	.123	.051	.144	2.417	.016	1.442
	Job.eva	.187	.050	.222	3.723	.000	1.442
3	Job.Des	.104	.050	.122	2.069	.039	1.457
	Job.eva	.156	.050	.186	3.136	.002	1.481
	Job.Spe	.160	.043	.190	3.758	.000	1.079
4	Job.Des	.101	.050	.119	2.011	.045	1.462
	Job.eva	.151	.050	.180	3.011	.003	1.499
	Job.Spe	.149	.044	.177	3.361	.001	1.164
	Job.Ana	.046	.048	.050	.953	.341	1.148
5	Rec. Pro	.461	.061	.368	7.540	.000	1.983

Thirdly, in the first step of the correlation coefficient $R = .396$ indicates a considerable degree of correlation between affective commitment and the organizational performance. The value of R-Square shows the degree of variation in the organizational performance which has explained by affective commitment. The value of $R^2 = 0.157$ suggests that (15.7%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained and interpreted by affective commitment. In the step 2, the correlation coefficient $R = .417$ has further increased with the addition of normative commitment. The value of R-Square = 0.174 suggests that (17.4%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained by affective commitment and normative commitment. In step 3, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.451$ has increased due to the addition of continuance commitment. The value of R-Square = 0.203 suggests that (20.3%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained by affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.396 ^a	.157	.155	.519643
2	.417 ^b	.174	.170	.515008
3	.451 ^c	.203	.197	.506582

The results of multiple regressions in the model have shown that affective commitment has positive significant ($B = 0.227$) effects on the organizational performance in manufacturing sector of Pakistan. In the second step, the addition of normative commitment has decreased the value of affective commitment from ($B = 0.262$) to ($B = 0.236$), while normative commitment has positive significant ($B = 0.089$) effects on the organizational performance. In step three, continuance commitment has positive significant ($B = 0.113$) effects on the organizational performance, while the effects of affective and normative commitments have dropped down. In conclusion, the employees commitment has positive significant ($B = .410$) effects on the organizational performance in manufacturing organizations.

Table 8: Results of Multiple Regressions

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Affect	.262	.032	.396	8.231	.000	1.000
2	Affect	.236	.033	.356	7.125	.000	1.095
	Normative	.089	.032	.137	2.753	.006	1.095
3	Affect	.235	.033	.355	7.225	.000	1.095
	Normative	.075	.032	.116	2.336	.020	1.112

	Continuance	.113	.031	.172	3.630	.000	1.017
	Emp. Com	.410	.048	.408	8.522	.000	1.83

The Regression Coefficient table allocates the required information to propose the significance of organizational performance by the employees commitment along with different determinant level. Employee's commitment contributes significantly to the regression model in a statistical association (by checking the "Sig." column) in the above table. The beta value of the data in the above table is very significant ($P \leq 0.000$, $B=0.410$). Thus, it can be concluded that there is positive significant relationship between the employee's commitment and organizational performance. Moreover, there is a casual and positive relationship among the variables. Thus, we are rejecting null hypothesis and accepting alternative hypothesis.

Finally, to test the mediating effects of employee's commitment on the relationship between recruitment process and organizational performance, the concept of Baron and Kenny's (1986) has wide popularity in literature and many researchers have applied for assessing mediation analysis. However, in the results of model summary, in the first step of the correlation coefficient $R = .320$ indicates a considerable degree of correlation between job description and the organizational performance. The value of R-Square shows the degree of variation in the organizational performance which has explained by job description. Reading the value of $R^2 = 0.103$ suggests that (10.3%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained and interpreted by job description. In the step 2, the correlation coefficient $R = .378$ has further increased with the addition of job evaluation. The value of R-Square = 0.143 suggests that (14.3%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained by job description and job evaluation. In step 3, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.541$ has increased due to the addition of job specification. The value of R-Square = 0.292 suggests that (29.2%) of the variance in organizational performance can be explained by job description, job evaluation, job specification. In the fourth step, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.541$ has remained the same even with the addition of job analysis and no further changes were noted in the value of R-Square. In the fifth step, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.583$ has increased with the addition of affective commitment. The value of R-Square = 0.340 suggests that (34.0%) of the variance in the organizational performance can be explained by job description, job evaluation, job specification, job analysis and affective commitment. In the sixth step, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.586$ has slightly increased with the addition of normative commitment. The value of R-Square = 0.343 suggests that (34.3%) of the variance in the organizational performance can be explained by job description, job evaluation, job specification, job analysis, affective and normative commitment. In the seventh step, the value of correlation coefficient $R = 0.601$ has increased with the addition of continuance commitment. The value of R-Square = 0.361 suggests that (36.1%) of the variance in the organizational performance can be explained by job description, job evaluation, job specification, job analysis, affective, normative and continuance commitment

Table 9: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.320 ^a	.103	.100	.536094
2	.378 ^b	.143	.138	.524773
3	.541 ^c	.292	.286	.477428
4	.541 ^d	.293	.285	.477975
5	.583 ^e	.340	.331	.462332
6	.586 ^f	.343	.332	.461773
7	.601 ^g	.361	.349	.456086

The results of multiple regressions in model have shown that job description has positive significant ($B = 0.274$) effects on the organizational performance in manufacturing sector of Pakistan. In the second step, the addition of job evaluation has decreased the value of job description from ($B = 0.274$) to ($B = 0.160$), while job evaluation has positive significant ($B = 0.203$) effects on the organizational performance. In step three, job specification has positive significant ($B = 0.340$) effects on the organizational performance, while the effects of job description and job evaluation have dropped down. In the fourth step, job analysis has positive insignificant ($B = 0.018$) effects on the organizational performance, while the values of other variables have slightly dropped down. In the step fifth, the affective commitment has positive significant ($B = 0.156$) effects on the organizational performance, while the values of all other variable dropped down. Therefore, it can be concluded that affective commitment mediates the relationship between job description, job evaluation, job specification, job analysis and the organizational performance. In the step sixth, the normative commitment has positive insignificant ($B = 0.040$) effects on the organizational performance, while the values of other variables dropped down but only job analysis remain the same. Therefore, it can be concluded that normative commitment mediates the relationship between job description, job evaluation, job specification, job analysis and the organizational performance. In the seventh step of multiple regression analysis, continuance commitment has positive significant ($B = 0.089$) effects on the organizational performance, while the values of other variables

dropped down but the values of job description and affective commitment has increased as compared to step sixth of the results. Therefore, it can be concluded that continuance commitment mediates the relationship between job evaluation, job specification, job analysis and the organizational performance. However, it can be concluded that employees commitment mediates the relationship between recruitment process and organizational performance in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan .

Table 10: Results of Multiple Regressions

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Job.Des	.274	.042	.320	6.454	.000	1.000
2	Job.Des	.160	.050	.188	3.215	.001	1.442
	Job.eva	.203	.049	.240	4.108	.000	1.442
3	Job.Des	.120	.046	.141	2.633	.009	1.457
	Job.eva	.139	.045	.164	3.050	.002	1.481
	Job.Spec	.340	.039	.402	8.750	.000	1.079
4	Job.Des	.119	.046	.139	2.602	.010	1.462
	Job.eva	.137	.046	.162	2.981	.003	1.499
	Job.Spec	.335	.040	.397	8.304	.000	1.164
	Job.Ana	.018	.044	.020	.415	.678	1.148
5	Job.Des	.089	.045	.104	1.994	.047	1.488
	Job.eva	.104	.045	.123	2.319	.021	1.531
	Job.Spec	.300	.040	.354	7.545	.000	1.202
	Job.Ana	.014	.043	.015	.325	.746	1.148
	Affect	.156	.031	.235	5.084	.000	1.165
6	Job.Des	.086	.045	.101	1.932	.054	1.491
	Job.eva	.098	.045	.116	2.175	.030	1.546
	Job.Spec	.295	.040	.349	7.424	.000	1.210
	Job.Ana	.012	.043	.013	.291	.771	1.149
	Affect	.147	.031	.221	4.681	.000	1.221
	Contin	.040	.029	.062	1.368	.172	1.138
7	Job.Des	.089	.044	.104	2.009	.045	1.492
	Job.eva	.094	.044	.111	2.107	.036	1.547
	Job.Spec	.288	.039	.340	7.316	.000	1.214
	Job.Ana	.003	.042	.003	.067	.947	1.155
	Affect	.149	.031	.224	4.804	.000	1.221
	Contin	.031	.029	.047	1.048	.295	1.150
	Continuance	.089	.028	.136	3.164	.002	1.031
8	Rec. Pro	.503	.059	.399	8.465	.000	1.54
	Emp. Com	.263	.047	.261	5.549	.000	1.38

The conclusion from that results of mediation test reveals that employee's commitment partially mediate the relationship between recruitment process and organizational performance because the correlation between recruitment process and the organizational performance has decreased and significant due to the effect of mediator, and all three correlations between independent, mediator, and dependent are statically significant ($\rho \leq 0.05$), thus, a partial mediation effect exists in this study which verify the conceptions of prior studies (Hayes, 2013).

5. Discussion

This study has operationalized the recruitment and selection process in the four sub-constructs namely a) job specification, b) job description, c) job evaluation, and d) job analysis and organizational performance is operationalized in three sub-constructs namely a) financial performance, b) job performance, and c) operational performance. The study has investigated the impact of recruitment and selection process on the organizational performance in Pakistani context. The findings of the study have shown agreement with the hypothesized results that the recruitment and selection process has positive significant relationship with the organizational performance in Pakistan manufacturing sector. The findings of the study are in line with prior investigations that recruitment and selection of employees in an organization is not only to add the number of employees into workplace but to hire competent and talented individuals for the appropriate job in workplace to get a high level of performance and improve organizational commitment among employees. The findings of this study have also confirmed the fact that the improved recruitment and selection policies significantly enhance organizational products. Initially, if the organization becomes successful to hire competent and talented staff, it can be

supportive and easy for it to sustain their employees in long run by making them satisfy (Rioux & Bernthal, 1999). In the market of fierce competition, it is highly productive for organizations to understand all the aspects that can lead them towards the ultimate goal of its success by effectively competing with competitors (DeWit & Meyer, 2005). Thus, we can argue that the recruitment process in Pakistan manufacturing sector is a significant determinant of the organizational performance. Likewise, the normative commitment, continuous commitment, and affirmative commitment are used as the sub-constructs of the employee commitment. The findings of the study indicate that the employee commitment has significant impact on the organizational performance. As the committed employees are highly satisfied and they fulfill their job very well. However, in the present global economic setting, change in the organizational settings is continues procedure that need to help workers in the organizational hierarchy. The findings of the study are consistent in the context of commitment with the prior studies such as, Akintayo (2010) and Tumwesigye (2010) who have found employee commitment as a significant determinant of organizational performance. In addition, the findings from literature lead to a conclusion that recruitment and selection process can be internally proceeding over promotions and moving out the existing employee or by the referrals from current staff family members and friends. The outcome from this study indicated an existence of causal association between recruitment process and organizational performance, and this relationship is found significant and strong. It is important for the organization to maintain honesty with the employees during the attraction strategy to develop trust and commitment with the employees (Armstrong, 2000a). The induction process becomes significance in the beginning to recruit the employees (McGrath & Hammontree, 2016). This shows the importance of a fluid transition between the recruitment and selection process in forming commitment in the organizations of Pakistan.

5. The mediating role of employee's commitment between recruitment process and organizational performance

The empirical findings of this study revealed that recruitment process has an influence on the organizational performance. The outcome from this study has indicated an existence of causal association between recruitment process and organizational performance, and this relationship is found significant and strong. The results of the study show that organizational performance of the organization is influenced by operational performance, job performance and financial performance. In terms of financial performance, it has been observed that financial statements of manufacturing sectors are organized and prepared under standards of the financial accounting. In addition to that, the reward system of the organization also shows the financial bonuses, recognition and other financial schemes for the employees showing best performance. The empirical findings of this study have revealed that organizational performance is affected by the recruitment process which is further affected due to the mediating role of employee commitment. The outcome from this study indicated an existence of causal association between employee commitment and organizational performance as well as between organizational performance and recruitment process, and these two relationships are found significant and strong according to the analysis.

6. Conclusion

This study aims to evaluate the mediating effects of employee's commitment on the association between dependent and independent variables in the manufacturing sector at Pakistan. The study has collected data from the managerial staff in Hattar, Islamabad, and Lahore regions in the manufacturing sector. The results of the study indicated that recruitment process has positive significant relationship with employees commitment and organizational performance. Likewise, employees commitment has positive and statistically significant relationship with the organizational performance in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan. The results have clarified that employee's commitment has mediating effects on the relationship between recruitment process and organizational performance. The results of the study have revealed that the statistical terms of factor loading are acceptable. So, the results of the study highlight the importance of the recruitment process in making the employees committed to their jobs which can ultimately leads to enhance the organizational performance.

References

- Anitha, (2014), "Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance", *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 63 No. 3, pp. 308-323. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-01-2013-0008>
- Armstrong. M. (2000a). *The name has changed but has the game remained the same?*. 11th ed. London: Kogan Page Publisher.
- Ballantyne.I. S., Gilmore, & Williams.S. (2009). *Recruiting and selecting staff in organizations*. Human Resource Management. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173>
- Bernthal, P., Rioux, S. & Wellins, R. (1999). 'The leadership forecast: A benchmarking study', Pittsburg: Development Dimensions International.

- Biong, H., Nygaard, A., & Silkoset, R. (2010). The influence of retail management's use of social power on corporate ethical values, employee commitment, and performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 97(3), 341–363. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-010-0523-0>
- Blau, P. M. 1964. Exchange and power in social life. New York: John Wiley.
- Bogatova, M. (2017). Improving recruitment, selection and retention of employees (Unpublished bachelor's thesis). South Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences, Kouvola, Finland. Retrieved from <https://www.theseus.fi>
- Briffa, K. R., T. J. Osborn, F. H. Schweingruber, I. C. Harris, P. D. Jones, S. G. Shiyatov, and E. A. Vaganov (2001), Low frequency temperature variations from a northern tree-ring density network, *Geophys. J., Res.*, 106, 2929– 2941.
- Brown, S. P. (1996). A meta-analysis and review of organizational research on job involvement. *Psychological Bulletin*, 120(2), 235–255. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.120.2.235>.
- Carifio, J. & Perla, R.J. (2021). Ten Common Misunderstandings, Misconceptions, Persistent Myths and Urban Legends about Likert Scales and Likert Response Formats and their Antidotes, *Journal of Social Sciences* 3(3).
- Chen, H. H., Qiao, S., & Lee, A. H. I. (2014). The impacts of different R&D organizational structures on performance of firms: Perspective of absorptive capacity. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 25(1), 83-95. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hitech.2013.12.007>.
- Cohen, G. L. (2003). Party Over Policy: The Dominating Impact of Group Influence on Political Beliefs. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 85(5), 808–822. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.85.5.808>.
- Dayo Idowu Akintayo (2010), Work-family role conflict and organizational commitment among industrial workers in Nigeria, *Journal of Counseling Psychology* 2(1).
- De Wit B. and Meyer R. (2005), Strategy Synthesis, Resolving Strategy Paradoxes to Create Competitive Advantage, Thomson Learning, London
- Given, Lisa M. 2008. "Qualitative research methods." In *The Encyclopedia of Educational Psychology*, edited by Neil J. Salkind, 827-831. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Gould-Williams, J. (2003). The importance of HR practices and workplace trust in achieving superior performance: a study of public-sector organizations. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 14(1), 28-54.
- García-Morales, V. J., Jiménez-Barrionuevo, M. M., & Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez, L. (2012). Transformational leadership influence on organizational performance through organizational learning and innovation. *Journal of business research*, 65(7), 1040-1050.
- Hayes, A. F. (2013). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach*. Guilford Press.
- Kelliher, C., & Anderson, D. (2010). Doing more with less? Flexible working practices and the intensification of work. *Human Relations*, 63(1), 83–106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726709349199>
- Khandekar, A., & Sharma, A. (2006), Organizational learning and performance: Understanding Indian scenario in present global context, *Education and Training* 48(8/9):682-692.
- Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of Psychology*, 22 140, 55.
- Locke, E. A. (1970). Job satisfaction and job performance: A theoretical analysis. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 5(5), 484-500.
- McGrath, J. & Hammontree, G. (2016), Employees ARE: the process of attracting, retaining and engaging, Grand Rapid Business Journal. Accessed from: <https://grbj.com/opinion/employees-are-the-process-of-attracting-retaining-and-engaging/>.
- Meyer, J. P. & Allen, N. J. (1997). Commitment in the workplace: Theory, research, and application. London: Sage.
- Meyer, J.P. & Herscovitch, L. (2001). Commitment in the workplace: toward a general model. *Human Resources Management Review*. 11(3). 299-326.
- Molm, L. D. (2006). The Social Exchange Framework. In P. J. Burke (Ed.), *Contemporary social psychological theories* (pp. 24–45). Stanford University Press.
- Nijhof, W.J., Streumer, J. (2098), Key Qualifications in Work and Education, Springer.**
- Presslee, A., Vance, T. W., & Webb, R. A. (2013). The effects of reward type on employee goal setting, goal commitment, and performance. *Accounting Review*, 88(5), 1805-1831. <https://doi.org/10.2308/accr-50480>.
- Richard TMowday Richard MSteers Lyman WPorter (1979). **The measurement of organizational commitment, *Journal of Vocational Behavior* Volume 14, Issue 2, April 1979, Pages 224-247**
- Steers, R. M. (1977). Antecedents and outcomes of organizational commitment. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 22(1), 46–56. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391745>
-

Descriptive Statistic of Recruitment Process

Descriptive result of Recruitment process

N#	Phrase		
Job Description			
1	The recruitment strategy at my organization describes the job very well		
2	All vacant positions are described clearly		
3	Job description increases performance of employees		
4	I know the job description during my present responsibilities at workplace		
5	My organization use job feedback of performance based on job description		
Job Specification			
6	All business units at my organization use the same recruitment policy		
7	I understand how the job can be fulfilled accurately to perform in the work very well		
8	I received few training sessions in the recruitment department		
9	I asked many times what is required to me by the recruitment policy		
10	Before recruiting new employees, I remind myself about the requirements of the job		
Job Evaluation			
11	The proper implementation of recruitment process improves the performance of employees in my organization		
12	Employees at my organization who score high during assessment perform well in their work		
13	I was asked to answer interview questions, but I still need to know what exactly are my duties after the interview		
14	Before a post is evaluated interviews are conducted with the immediate supervisor		
15	Before a post is evaluated, interviews are conducted with the incumbent of post		
Job Analysis			
16	It is necessary to conduct briefing sessions before interview on the job post		
17	The best way to ensure awareness at all levels of the organization is to conduct briefing sessions with the groups of employees on the essence of the job evaluation system		
18	The communication process is critical to the successful implementation of the job evaluation system		
19	All employees involved with the writing of job descriptions need for training		
20	The analysis of job still requires to be done completely		

Descriptive Statistic of Employee Commitment

Descriptive result of employee commitment

No.	Phrase		
Affective Commitment			
1	This organization has a great deal of meaning for me		
2	I would be happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization		
3	I feel like a part of the family in this organization		
4	I feel a strong sense of belonging to this organization		
5	I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own		
6	This organization has a 'sentimental value' to me		
Normative Commitment			
7	I am afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without having another one lined up		

8	It would be very hard for me to leave this organization right now, even if I wanted to		
9	My life would be disrupted if I decide to leave this organization now		
10	Right now, staying with this organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire		
11	I feel that I have few options to consider leaving this organization		
12	One of the few serious consequences of leaving this organization would be scarcity of available alternatives		
Continuance Commitment			
13	I think people these days move from company to company too often		
14	I do believe that a person must change his/her organization regularly		
15	If I got another offer for a better job elsewhere I would feel it was right to leave the organization		
16	One of the main reasons I continue to work for this organization is that I believe that loyalty is important & therefore I feel a sense of moral obligation to remain		
17	I was taught to believe in the value of remaining loyal to one organization		
18	Things were better in the past when people stayed with one organization for most of their career life		

Descriptive Statistic of Organizational Performance

Descriptive result of organizational performance

No	Phrase		
Financial Performance			
1	The financial statements of the company are prepared in line with the financial accounting standards		
2	The financial statements are published regularly		
3	The capital structure of the company is appropriate		
4	The company has fully utilized the debt facility		
5	The company returns are profitable relative to its assets		
6	There are adequate company assets		
Job Performance			
7	I always be at work in time		
8	My performance is accessed daily by my supervisor		
9	My performance is limited by poor leadership of my supervisor		
10	My colleagues encourage me to perform		
11	Performance review improves job performance		
12	I can perform my tasks with difficulty		
Operational Performance			
13	I receive specific limited feedback from my manager on my past performance		
14	I could be more motivated after performance appraisal		
15	Promotion should be based on performance appraisal		
16	Performance reviews provide me with the opportunity to set personal goals		
17	Our company has a reward system that suggests financial bonuses for employees showing good performance		
18	The employees are assigned with innovation roles in their job description in our company		

Author Information

Fadillah Binti Ismail
FPTP, UTHM
Malaysia

Azhar Ud Din
Department of Management Sciences
Harbin Institute of Technology
China

Farwida Javed
COMSATS University
Attock Campus
Pakistan

Fazal ur Rehman
FPTP, UTHM
Malaysia

Muhammad Mujtaba Asad
Department of Education
IBA Sukkar University
Pakistan

Sadia Ijaz Shiekh
COMSATS University
Attock Campus
Pakistan
